

Notes on the red-spot hairy field spider *Neoscona triangula* (Keyserling, 1864) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: The red-spot hairy field spider *Neoscona triangula* (Keyserling, 1864) described as *Epeira triangula* from Mauritius is known throughout Africa. The species is commonly found in South Africa and its general morphology, web-building behaviour and distribution are discussed along with images of live specimens.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, Free State, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), web-building.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Neoscona* Simon, 1864 is a large genus known from 126 species and has a wide geographical distribution. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), a large number of specimens from several localities in South Africa were collected, many of which are members of the orb-web family Araneidae and the genus *Neoscona* (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). One of the species, with a distinct red marking ventrally on the abdomen, was regularly sampled and photographed at night during SANSa surveys. It was identified as the red-spot hairy field spiders *Neoscona triangula* (Keyserling, 1864). The species was originally described as *Epeira triangula* from Mauritius and it has since been recorded throughout Africa (Grasshoff, 1986; World Spider Catalog, 2022).

The species is commonly found in South Africa and its general morphology, web-building behaviour and distribution are discussed and illustrated along with photographs of live specimens.

METHODS

Photographs of the species in the SANSa Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) provided information on its morphology and behaviour. Voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA).

Observations on web-building behaviour was undertaken at Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE) in the Free State province. Most of the photographs were taken and observations made by the first author (AJ) while staying on the estate.

MORPHOLOGY

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: total length females 9–17 mm, males 7–9 mm. Carapace mottled, varies from creamish-brown to dark grey (Figs 1 & 3); densely covered with white setae; longitudinal thoracic fovea. Abdomen broad, rounded, longer than wide; mottled; clothed with fine setae with scattered longer setae in between; dorsum with both longitudinal and transverse blackish brown bands (Figs 3 & 8). Ventrally species is recognised by a red marking that varies in shape between specimens (Figs 2 & 4). Legs dorsally faintly banded; ventrally dark; with scattered setae. Female epigyne gradually narrowing towards the long scape (Figs 3–4). Male smaller than female; tibiae I and II with strong setae (Fig. 7); abdomen more oval than in female; with short dark transverse bands (Fig. 8).

Figs 1–4. *Neoscona triangula* female: 1 & 3. Dorsal views. 2 & 4. Ventral views. (Photos: 1. Peter Webb, 2. Les Oates, 3–4. Stefan Nesper)

Figs 5–9. *Neoscona triangula*: 5. Epigyne (after Grasshoff, 1986). 6. Epigyne. 7. Setae on tibiae I and II of male (after Grasshoff, 1986). 8. Male abdomen. 9. Female abdomen (8–9 after Grasshoff, 1986).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Neoscona triangula distribution in Africa (after Grasshoff, 1986).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Coega (-33.76, 25.65); East London (-33.01, 27.90); Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kasouga (-33.63, 26.43); Kwandwe Private Game Reserve (-33.09, 26.57); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61). **Free State:** Bethlehem (-28.23, 28.30); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.80, 27.65); Deneysville (-26.87, 28.09); Ficksburg (-28.86, 27.86); Oranjeville (-26.99, 28.20); Philipopolis (-30.25, 25.27); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Welkom (-27.97, 26.74). **Gauteng:** Benoni (-26.19, 28.31); Brakpan (-26.23, 28.37); Bronkhorstspruit, Farm Onverwacht (-25.80, 28.74); Dunnottar (-26.35, 28.47); Irene, Gem Village Field (25.85, 28.16); Johannesburg (-26.20, 28.04); Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Maraisburg (-26.11, 27.56); Midrand (-25.95, 28.14); Onderstepoort (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane, Rietondale Research Station (-25.73, 28.23); Randburg (-26.07, 27.92); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodepoort (-26.14, 27.86); Witwatersrand Botanical Gardens (-26.20, 28.04). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ashburton (-29.60, 30.38); Botha Hill (-29.48, 30.50); Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Giant's Cup Wilderness Reserve (-29.97, 29.46); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.70); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25);

iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40, 32.76); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pongola, Farm Vergeval (-27.35, 31.61); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47).

Limpopo: Bela-Bela, Highland Estate (-24.83, 28.17); Dendron, Farm Amsterdam (-23.37, 29.32); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Leggalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pietersburg/Polokwane (-23.89, 29.46); Springbok Flats, Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46). **Mpumalanga:** Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Ermelo (-26.51, 29.98); Komatipoort, Farm Sommerreg (-25.53, 31.82); Kriel (-26.25, 29.26); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22). **Northern Cape:** Kameeldrift (-29.38, 23.80); Kleinsee (-29.67, 17.07). **Western Cape:** Bellville (-33.90, 18.63); Caledon (-34.24, 19.43); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Fish Hoek, Peer Hill (-34.05, 18.35); Hermanus (-34.40, 19.25); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Knysna (-34.03, 23.00); Murraysburg (-31.96, 23.75); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.35, 21.67); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48); Tsitsikamma National Park (-33.98, 23.52); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

HABITAT

During SANSa surveys, the species was sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket Biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). The species was also sampled from crops such as avocado, macadamia and pecan orchards, and onion, sorghum and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

BEHAVIOUR

They construct large orb-webs at night in vegetation. They remove the web early in the morning and rest during the day on plants nearby (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009). In South Africa, they are very commonly seen in gardens during the summer months.

Figs 10–11. *Neoscona triangula* female in a large orb-web. (Photos: Allen Jones)

WEB BUILDING

The following observations were made at Mpetsane by the first author (AJ) and a series of photographs were taken. The female was observed first on 2 January 2022 resting on a curly dock (*Rumex crispus*) plant stalk.

Each evening at approximately 8 pm the female climbed to the top of the stalk, and from the high point she turned and then produced a long (1.2–1.4 m) single silk thread that drifted outwards and downwards until it settled on a nearby plant leaf or stem. She then climbed along it until she reached the middle, where she then dropped vertically to lower-level plant leaves to anchor the thread. She repeated this exercise several times, anchoring the “main line” to nearby foliage. She then climbed halfway up, approximately 200 mm below the main line. From this point, she began to create some 17–20 parallel radial threads until she had created an orb-web some 400 mm in diameter. The web was secured by the anchor lines attached to the foliage. This all happened within 15 to 20 minutes. She then lay down the sticky spirals (Figs 10–11). She produced some 30 m of silk to create her masterpiece.

She remained in the web until just before dawn (6 am) when she began to gather the silk webbing together. She started at the central hub and worked her way around the radials, rolling the silk into a bundle (almost as large as herself). She then gathers the anchor lines, sometimes leaving the “main anchor line” in place. When she had collected all the silk, she carefully climbs down the stalk, pausing to fix the silk bundle to the vegetation (Figs 12–13). She continues downwards until she reaches the base on the stalk. She then remains hidden during the day until dusk.

Figs 12–13. *Neoscona triangula* female gathering the silk webbing and transporting it to the plant below. (Photos: Allen Jones)

The next day at sunset she became active but this time she carried her silk bundle with her. She repeated the exercise of web-building but it seems that she unwound strands from the bundle and used some of them to produce her fairly symmetrical vertical orb-web with a diameter of 400 to 450 mm. She repeated this exercise nightly for several nights, then reverted to producing new silk to make a fresh web. During a period of heavy rain and strong wind at night she stopped working until it was over, then resumed web building, often losing several hours of potential prey catching.

Some interesting adaptations to web building were made by the female. On several occasions she produced a web of which only half of the orb was symmetrical, having the regular radii (7–10), while the other half consisted of irregular silk threads (Figs 14–15). This “half-web” was often left in place at dawn and not removed.

Figs 14–15. *Neoscona triangula* female in a half orb-web. (Photos: Allen Jones)

After 23 days, the female left this site and produced a 5.35-m-long thread 1.5 m above the ground on a nearby tree. From there she then travelled to an apricot tree and in tandem with other *N. triangula* already resident there. She continued making large, full orb-webs. There were several *N. triangula* in the vicinity and they also occasionally made half orb-webs. These spiders seem to prey mainly on moths at night (Figs 16–17).

Figs 16–17. *Neoscona triangula* female in her web feeding on a moth. (Photos: Johan van Zyl)

CONSERVATION

The species has a wide distribution throughout Africa, and in South Africa it occurs in >20 protected areas such as the Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999); Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005) and Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020) and there are no significant threats to the species.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Johan van Zyl and the late Peter Webb, Les Oates and Stefan Naser who shared their photographs.

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